

A MODEL OF SEQUENCE IN THE PROCESS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING IN THE PRACTICE OF HIGHER VACATIONAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: Improvement of professional competence of students on the basis of sequence, methods of growing professional competence of students on the basis of sequence in the process of learning the Russian language.

Keywords: consistency, sequence, methods, Russian language, Russian language learning, competence

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

The Sequence (consistency) – is building on previous knowledge as to apply and develop existing knowledge, skills and abilities in such a way that various connections are made in the minds of students, the main ideas of the course are revealed, old and new knowledge interact, resulting in thorough and deep knowledge. As a result, strong education system will be formed.

In the scientific works of many scientists, like S.Y.Alferov, A.P.Vladislavlev, B.S.Gershunsky, S.M.Godnik, the main source of continuing education, the reasons for its occurrence, the main stages of development, their specific features are defined, and the current state of the phenomenon under study is described in terms of historical perspectives. U.I.Inoyatov, V.M.Karimova, N.R.Rakhmanova, B.M.Umarov, whose works are dedicated to some aspects of the continuing educational process.

One of the bright tendencies of the current development of professional education is its regionalization, which is essentially expressed as a response to the needs of the region, its population, to improve the educational system in the region as a “tool” for their own development.

The principle of regionalization of professional education covers a number of aspects of the activity of educational institutions in new socio-economic conditions.

Implementation of the single concept of continuous education and the principle of consistency of all steps in it will help to solve the main task of modern Uzbekistan education - to modernize it and increase its effectiveness.

It should be noted that the retrospective analysis of foreign and domestic psychological-pedagogical literature showed that consistency is studied as the

interdependence of the past, present and future in the teaching process, or as the sequence of students' acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities.

After the recognition of consistency as a didactic principle in modern education, its importance has greatly increased.

Aiming to develop his professional knowledge, the student should do the following while studying a foreign language (Russian):

- pronunciation of the sound characteristic of the field of vocational activity, features of intonation, features of the pronunciation method;
- mastering the vocational lexicon, fixed combinations, phraseological units of professional terminology;
- mastering the technique of translation (with a dictionary) of professionally oriented texts with various levels of access to their content;
- mastering grammar skills that ensure communication without distorting the meaning in written and oral communication of a general nature; the main grammatical events typical for professional speech;
- learning to understand dialogic and monologic speech in order to extract necessary information in professional activity;
- mastering the written speech and acquiring the skills of recording and transmitting information of various sizes and characteristics in written form by creating annotations, abstracts, theses, reports.

The epistemological essence of scientific models is that they tell about the body, its functions, properties, etc. enables systematic expression of knowledge. The main task of the model – is to explain the set of information related to the subject of knowledge.

Speaking about the theoretical basis of the creation of the model, it should be mentioned that the modernization of education envisages a radical renewal of the content and structure of professional education.

We study the model of consistency of Russian language learning not separately from the model of the educational process in vocational education institutions, but together with it. This means that when describing the pedagogical conditions for the implementation of consistency, we rely on modern ideas about the organization of the educational process (taking into account the principles of education, the state standard of general and vocational education, modern methods and forms of education, etc.). This allowed us to present a model of sequence in teaching the Russian language from the point of view of the main components of the educational process (goal, content, etc.) and participants of the pedagogical process (teacher and student).

Analyzing the implementation of sequence in the main directions of the educational process, we proposed our own model of implementation of consistency in teaching of the Russian language. As a basis for the creation of the model, we

took the idea that the student/learner should constantly advance in his development, passing from one level to another level, from one level of knowledge to another, in the process of vocational training.

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